

Investigation of Alpha, Beta, Gamma Radiation Shielding by using G-M Counter and PHITS Program Code

Lwun Htet Nay Aung^{*}, Khin Moe Oo^{**}, Hla Htay Win^{***}, Thei` Theint Theint Aung^{****}

Abstract

The interaction of the various radiations with matter is uniquely determined by their penetrating through matter and consequently. The type and amount of shielding materials need for radiation protection. In this research, the properties of alpha, beta, gamma radiations will be studied and determined how to protect these radiations. In this research, density and width of the shielding material will be analyzed by using paper, aluminum, lead, the G-M counter (ST-360) and source of (Co_{60}). And also, the density and width of the shielding material was designed by using the PHITS (particle and heavy ion transport code system) for checking of G-M counter experiment results.

Introduction

Introduction of Particle and Heavy Ion Transport Code System

Particle and heavy ion transport code are essential implement in design and study of spacecrafts and accelerator facilities. We have therefore developed the multi-purpose Monte Carlo Particle and Heavy Ion Transport code System, PHITS based on the (NMTC/JAM.3) The physical processes which we should deal with in a multipurpose simulation code can be divided into two categories, transport process and collision process. In the transport process, PHITS can simulate a motion under external fields such as magnetic and gravity. Without the external fields, neutral particles move along a straight trajectory with constant energy up to the next collision point. However, charged particles and heavy ions interact many times with electrons in the material losing energy and changing direction. PHITS treats ionization processes not as collision but as a transport process under an external field. The average dE/dx is given by the charge density of the material and the momentum of the particle. The second category of the physical processes is the collision with the nucleus in the material. In addition to the collision, we consider the decay of the particle as a process in this category. The total reaction cross section, or the life time of the particle is an essential quantity in the determination of the mean free path of the transport particle. According to the mean free path, PHITS chooses the next collision point using the Monte Carlo method. To generate the secondary particles of the collision, we need the information on the final states of the collision. For neutron induced reactions in low energy region, PHITS employs the cross sections from Evaluated Nuclear Data libraries. For high energy neutrons and other particles, we have incorporated two models, JAM4) and JQMD5) to simulate the particle induced reactions up to 200 GeV and the nucleus-nucleus collisions, respectively. Recently PHITS introduces an event generator for particle transport parts in the low energy region. Thus, PHITS was completely rewritten for the introduction of the event generator for neutron-induced reactions in energy region less than 20 MeV. Furthermore, several new tallies were incorporated for estimation of the relative biological effects. This report includes descriptions on new features and functions introduced into the code. For examples, GG geometry, parallelization, DPA tally, neutron, photon and electron transportation, and detailed descriptions how to setup the geometry as

* Lecturer, Department of Physics, Bago University

** Dr., Associate Professor, Department of Physics, Bago University

*** Dr., Lecturer, Department of Physics, Bago University

**** Assistant Lecturer, Department of Physics, Bago University

well. In order to keep comprehensive descriptions as the manual of PHITS, this report includes description on some parts of the NMTC/JAM code, which is an origin of code structure of PHITS.

The source code of PHITS is written in Fortran, and can be compiled and executed on various operating system, such as Windows, Mac and Linux. For Windows and Mac, the executable file compiled by Intel Fortran was included in the PHITS package. Thus, you can execute PHITS in Windows and Mac without compiling it. For Linux, you must compile PHITS by yourself using make command coupled with an appropriate Fortran compiler.

PHITS can be executed on Windows (XP or later), Mac (OS X v10.5 or later), Linux, and Unix operating systems. Recommended system requirements for PHITS are 2GB of RAM and 6GB (at least 3GB is required) of available space on hard disk. There is no software you have to pre-install before using PHITS. However, we recommend you to install a text editor that can display line numbers, since line number is specified if you make a mistake in your PHITS input file. Furthermore, installation of Ghost script and GSview is required to display image files created by PHITS, which are written in the EPS format.

Introduction of Geiger-Muller Counters

A Geiger counter (Geiger-Muller tube) is a device used for the detection and measurement of all types of radiation: alpha, beta and gamma radiation. Basically, it consists of a pair of electrodes surrounded by a gas. The electrodes have a high voltage across them. The gas used is usually Helium or Argon. When radiation enters the tube, it can ionize the gas. The ions (and electrons) are attracted to the electrodes and an electric current is produced. A scaler counts the current pulses, and one obtains a "count" whenever radiation ionizes the gas. The apparatus consists of two parts, the tube and the (counter + power supply). The Geiger-Mueller tube is usually cylindrical, with a wire down the centre. The (counter + power supply) have voltage controls and timer options. Figure 1 was shown the G-M counter Mode-ST360

Working Principle of The Giger-Muller Counter

When ionizing radiation such as an alpha, beta or gamma particle enters the tube, it can ionize some of the gas molecules in the tube. From these ionized atoms, an electron is knocked out of the atom, and the remaining atom is positively charged. The high voltage in the tube produces an electric field inside the tube. The electrons that were knocked out of the atom are attracted to the positive electrode, and the positively charged ions are attracted to the negative electrode. This produces a pulse of current in the wires connecting the electrodes, and this pulse is counted. After the pulse is counted, the charged ions become neutralized, and the Geiger counter is ready to record another pulse. In order for the Geiger counter tube to restore itself quickly to its original state after radiation has entered, a gas is added to the tube. For proper use of the Geiger counter, one must have the appropriate voltage across the electrodes. If the voltage is too low, the electric field in the tube is too weak to cause a current pulse. If the voltage is too high, the tube will undergo continuous discharge, and the tube can be damaged. Usually the manufacture recommends the correct voltage to use for the tube. Larger tubes require larger voltages to produce the necessary electric fields inside the tube. In class should do an experiment to determine the proper operating voltage. First, is placed a radioactive isotope in the Geiger-Mueller tube. Then, will slowly vary the voltage across the tube and measure the counting rate. For low voltages, no counts are recorded. This is because the electric field is too weak for even one pulse to be recorded. As the voltage is increased, eventually one obtains a counting rate. The voltage at which the G-M tube just begins to count is called the starting potential. The counting rate quickly rises as the voltage is increased. For our equipment, the rise is so fast, that the graph looks like a step potential. After the quick rise,

the counting rate levels off. This range of voltages is termed the plateau region. Eventually, the voltage becomes too high and we have continuous discharge. The threshold voltage is the voltage where the plateau region begins. Proper operation is when the voltage is in the plateau region of the curve. For best operation, the voltage should be selected fairly close to the threshold voltage, and within the first 1/4 of the way into the plateau region. A rule we follow with the G-M tubes in our lab is the following: for the larger tubes to set the operating voltage about 75 Volts above the starting potential; for the smaller tubes to set the operating voltage about 50 volts above the starting potential. In the plateau region the graph of counting rate vs. voltage is in general not completely flat. The plateau is not a perfect plateau. In fact, the slope of the curve in the plateau region is a measure of the quality of the G-M tube. For a good G-M tube, the plateau region should rise at a rate less than 10 percent per 100 volts. That is, for a change of 100 volts, $(\Delta \text{counting rate})/(\text{average counting rate})$ should be less than 0.1. An excellent tube could have the plateau slope as low as 3 percent per 100 volts.

Experimental Method

Nuclear radiation is ionizing radiation. Ionizing radiation is radiation that can strip electrons from atoms and molecules. Gamma (and x-rays) are ultrashort electromagnetic radiation. They have great penetrating power and can easily pass through the body and are attenuated by dense materials such as lead. Beta particles are electrons. Beta particles have a net negative charge. They have low penetrating power. Most beta radiation can be blocked by 1/8" (4mm) of aluminum. Alpha particles are massive particles consisting of two neutrons and two protons. Alpha particles have a net positive charge. They are equivalent to the nucleus of a helium atom. Alpha particles have a low penetration power. A few inches of air or a piece of paper can effectively block alpha particles.

Step-1: The first source we will use is the Co-60 alpha particle source. Co-60 has a half-life of 5.27 years and activity with 0.1 μ Ci. The alpha particle source will need to face the window of the GM tube inside the wand. It will need to be in close proximity to the window. I needed to move my source to a distance of only 1.5 cm away from the mica window of the GM tube to get a significant CPM reading above background. Next place a paper shield of approximately 0.01cm thickness in-between the source and GM tube then record results.

Step-2: Next use the Co-60 beta source. I place this source 4 cm from the front of the GM tube. Next place the paper shield in front of the beta source. Record your results. Next place an Aluminum shield of approximately (0.3cm) thickness in-between the source and GM tube, then record results.

Step-3: Next use the Co-60 gamma source. I placed this source 3 cm from the front of the GM tube. Take CPM readings as before. Record your results. Next place a lead shield of approximately (0.6 cm) thickness in-between the source and GM tube and record results.

Figure .1 Step-1 Alpha Particle Shielding Test

Figure .2 Step-2 Beta Radiation Shielding Test

Figure .3 Step-3 Gamma Radiation Shielding Test

Figure .4 G-M Counter ST-360

Figure .5 Radiation Counting without Shielding Materials

Figure .6 Radiation Counting with Shielding Materials

Theoretical Method

FORTRAN came to dominate this area of programming early on and has been in continuous use for over six decades in computationally intensive areas such as numerical weather prediction, finite element analysis, computational fluid dynamics, computational physics, crystallography and computational chemistry. It is a popular language for high-performance computing and is used for programs that benchmark and rank the world's fastest supercomputers. In this section, for theoretical method was used the Fortran program code, PHITS simulation. Free Fortran format is very useful in nuclear simulation software. Firstly, write the Fortran (formula translation) program by using with density of shielding material, width of shielding material, activity of Co_{60} sources, half-life of the sources, and etc. Then completely Fortran file is compiled in the PHITS. After that, PHITS gave the output file with numerical data file, text file and graphic file for radiation shielding experiment.

Figure .7 Step-2 Beta Radiation Shielding Test

Figure .8 Step-1 Alpha Particle Shielding Test

Figure .8 Radiation Counting without Shielding Materials

Figure .9 PHITS Data output File

Figure .10 Alpha particle Shielding Width

Figure .11 Beta Radiation Shielding Width

Figure .12 Gamma Radiation Shielding Width

Results and Discussion

Type of Radiation	Results from Experiment	Results from PHITS
Alpha Particle	Paper width=0.01cm	Paper width=0.005cm
Beta Radiation	Aluminum width=0.3 cm	Aluminum width=0.3 cm
Gamma Radiation	Lead width=0.6cm	Lead width=0.6cm

Gamma (and x-rays) are ultrashort electromagnetic radiation. They have great penetrating power and can easily pass through the body and are attenuated by dense materials. Only can stop with such as lead of width 0.6cm. Beta particles are electrons. Beta particles have a net negative charge. They have low penetrating power. Most beta radiation can be blocked by (0.3cm) of aluminum. Alpha particles have a low penetration power. A few inches of air or a piece of paper can effective block alpha particles.

Conclusion

The width of the shielding material from experimental results are nearly equal to width of PHITS simulation program code. Common sense on the shielding profiles of α , β and γ rays has been confirmed by PHITS simulations. PHITS is useful for particle transport simulation in a mixed radiation field owing to its applicability to various radiation types.

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my sincere thanks to Dr Aye Aye Tun, Rector, Bago University, for her kind permission to carry out this research. I would like to express my sincere thanks to Dr Yin Yin Than, Pro-Rector, Bago University, for helpful advice and valuable guidance. I would like to thank Professor Dr Khin Htoo, Head of Department of Physics, Bago University, for her kind permission to carry out this work.

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